

Mucilage appearance in the Adriatic Sea during Summer 2024

Fig. 1. Floating macroaggregates at Passetto (N Adriatic Sea).

During the summer 2024, the Adriatic Sea experienced the ‘dirty sea’ phenomenon, characterized by the formation of large mucilage aggregates in the water column (Fig. 1). This event, which has occurred periodically since 1729, has been particularly extensive during recent decades, especially between 1988–1990 and 1999–2002. Beginning in June 2024 near the Croatian coast of Rovinj, the mucilage aggregates spread following the typical counterclockwise circulation, moving through the Gulf of Trieste, the Venice Lagoon, the Emilia Romagna and Marche coasts, and eventually reaching as far south as Apulia.

Similar to other regions (Marmara Sea, Aegean Sea, NW Mediterranean, and New Zealand), this phenomenon began with a bloom of the dinoflagellate *Gonyaulax fragilis* (formerly reported as *G. hyalina* [1]) (Fig. 2). As

Fig. 2. *Gonyaulax fragilis* in mucilage samples (LM micrographs).

the bloom declined, the rupture of the thecae released sticky polysaccharide-rich cytoplasmic content [2]. This material formed aggregates, embedding the marine snow already abundant in the water column. The aggregation process, facilitated by a stable, stratified water column and reduced circulation, led to the formation of larger aggregates such as macroflocs (Fig. 3), stringers (Fig. 4), clouds (Fig. 5), etc. [3]. When these ag-

Fig. 3. Mucilage macroflocs in the upper water column and at surface.

gregates settled onto the seafloor, they potentially caused harm to benthic organisms.

After the initial phase, *G. fragilis* was no longer detectable in the mucus, except for the presence of its empty thecae. Instead, the aggregates became colonized by a diatom-dominated microalgal community, primarily *Nitzschia gobbii* and *Thalassionema nitzschioides*. This community was similar to the surrounding water, but exhibited abundances up to three orders of magnitude higher [4]. Mucus provides an ideal microenvironment for microbial growth, where efficient nutrient recycling by bacteria supports the proliferation of microalgae [5].

As usual, this mucilage event was highly dynamic. Aggregates shifted in shape, consistency, and location throughout the day due to wind and currents, moving up and down the water column depending on its turbulence and stability. The phenomenon persisted for approximately three months. Although classified as a non-toxic harmful algal bloom (HAB), the mucilage had significant impacts. It disrupted tourism and hindered fishing activities by clogging nets and other gear. Moreover, an unprecedented mortality of wild mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) along the Conero Riviera was observed toward the end of the mucilage event (Fig. 6). This mortality was likely linked to the

Fig. 4. Stringers in the water column.

Fig. 5. Clouds of mucilage floating in the mixed layer.

Fig. 6. Mortality of wild mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) on the rocky bottom.

combination of exceptionally high temperatures and the suffocating effect of the mucilage on filter feeders.

Although mucilage aggregates were observed throughout the entire water column (in the mixed layer, at the thermocline, and in the bottom layer), mucilage events in the Adriatic Sea are of pelagic origin. They should not be confused with benthic mucilage, such as observed e.g. in the Tyrrhenian Sea, where mucus covering benthic organisms and substrata is produced locally by benthic chrysophytes and/or ectocarpalean macroalgae.

References

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